

DETERMINANTS OF ART ADHERENCE IN HIV-INFECTED CHILDREN: A SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC ANALYSIS

L.N. Tuychiev¹, G.K. Khudaykulova², D.B. Fayzullaeva³, Kh.M. A. Sadikov⁴

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Infectious and Pediatric Infectious Diseases, Tashkent State Medical University. Uzbekistan, Tashkent¹

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of Public Health and Management, Tashkent State Medical University. Uzbekistan, Tashkent²

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Specialist at the Republican AIDS Center of Uzbekistan³

Assistant at the Department of Infectious and Pediatric Infectious Diseases, Tashkent State Medical University. Uzbekistan, Tashkent⁴

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15570898>

Abstract. To determine the influence of socio-demographic factors on the formation of adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) among HIV-infected children in Uzbekistan. The study included HIV-infected children and adolescents receiving ART. Adherence was assessed based on gender, age, place of residence, family composition, income level, characteristics of caregivers, and their education level. Data analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics software. Statistical methods included descriptive statistics, chi-square test, Student's t-test, and correlation analysis with the construction of a mathematical model to identify associations and predict risk. ART adherence was significantly associated with several socio-demographic factors. The highest adherence was observed among children from complete families (66.7%; $p < 0.01$), those from middle- and high-income families (70.6%; $p < 0.001$), when therapy was self-managed by adolescents (90.3%; $p < 0.001$), and when caregivers had higher education ($p < 0.001$). Intergroup differences were statistically significant. The constructed model showed moderate and weak but meaningful correlations ($r = 0.53$; $r = 0.38$), which may be useful for predictive purposes. Socio-demographic factors significantly influence ART adherence in HIV-infected children. The developed model may be used for early identification of risk groups and for optimizing pediatric ART support programs.

Keywords: antiretroviral therapy, HIV, children, adherence, social determinants, mathematical model, SPSS, correlation.

INTRODUCTION

Antiretroviral therapy (ART) remains the only effective method for treating HIV infection, as it helps reduce viral load, improve immune function, and enhance the quality of life for patients. However, achieving optimal ART effectiveness depends largely on high adherence, particularly in pediatric populations, where compliance often relies not only on the patient but also on their surrounding environment [1].

In recent years, thanks to the implementation of national programs for the prevention of mother-to-child HIV transmission, the rate of infant HIV infection in Uzbekistan has significantly decreased. However, a new challenge has emerged — ensuring long-term disease control in adolescents living with HIV. In this context, investigating the factors influencing ART adherence in children has become particularly relevant [2].

Of special interest is the role of socio-demographic factors — such as gender, age, place of residence, family structure, income level, and education of caregivers — which may significantly influence adherence. While the importance of these variables has been recognized in international literature, they remain understudied in the national context, hindering the development of locally adapted support programs [3].

Despite significant progress in expanding ART access for children living with HIV, adherence remains one of the key factors determining treatment success and long-term outcomes. Poor adherence is particularly problematic in pediatric practice, where treatment compliance is largely dependent on the child's immediate environment — family, guardians, and healthcare providers.

Numerous international studies emphasize that various socio-demographic determinants — including the educational level of caregivers, family composition, socioeconomic status, and the level of child involvement — impact adherence [1,3,4]. However, in low-resource settings such as Uzbekistan, these issues remain insufficiently explored.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was designed as a cross-sectional observational investigation focused on assessing the influence of socio-demographic factors on adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) among HIV-infected children.

Data were collected at a specialized clinic affiliated with the Republican AIDS Center in Tashkent. The study included 695 HIV-positive children and adolescents under regular follow-up care and receiving ART. Data collection was conducted between 2021 and 2024 via review of medical records and questionnaires completed by adolescents and, when necessary, their legal guardians.

Inclusion criteria:

- Confirmed HIV diagnosis;
- Age from 0 to 18 years;
- At least 6 months of ART;
- Availability of complete medical records;
- Provision of informed consent to participate.

Exclusion criteria:

- Severe cognitive impairment limiting communication;
- Lack of consent to participate.

The following variables were assessed:

- ART adherence level (high, moderate, low);
- Age, gender, place of residence (urban/rural);
- Family status (complete, incomplete, orphan);
- Household income level (low, below average, average, high);
- Identity of person administering ART (self, parents, relatives, healthcare providers);
- Educational level of the treatment supervisor.

Statistical analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics v.26. The following methods were applied:

- Descriptive statistics (frequencies, proportions, means);
- Chi-square (χ^2) test for comparing categorical variables;
- Student's t-test for analyzing differences in quantitative variables;

- Pearson correlation coefficient (r) for determining the strength and direction of associations;
- Construction of a predictive mathematical model based on statistically significant predictors.

A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the context of adolescent HIV care in Uzbekistan, identifying the factors that contribute to long-term adherence among children and teenagers is particularly important. Understanding which socio-demographic characteristics are associated with high or low levels of ART adherence is of both theoretical and practical value for designing targeted patient support programs.

This study presents a comprehensive assessment of the impact of socio-demographic factors on ART adherence in HIV-infected children. Variables such as place of residence, family structure, income level, the identity of the person ensuring ART intake, and their educational background were analyzed. The findings helped identify social determinants that require special attention in structuring effective support systems for pediatric patients living with HIV.

The results of the analysis of family structure among study participants are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of HIV-Infected Children Included in the Study by Family Status

The majority of children included in the study were raised in complete families (61.9%). The proportion of children living in state institutions (orphans) was extremely low (0.9%).

Next, we analyzed ART adherence levels in relation to the family status of the children (see Table 1).

Table 1. Family Status of HIV-Infected Children Included in the Study

Family Status / Adherence Level	Low (n)	Low (%)	Moderate (n)	Moderate (%)	High (n)	High (%)
Complete	54	49.5±4.8	102	58.3±3.7	274	66.7±2.3**
Incomplete	49	45.0±4.8	73	41.7±3.7	137	33.3±2.3*
Orphan	6	5.5±2.2	0	-	0	-

Note: — statistically significant difference compared to the low adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ** — $p < 0.01$; *** — $p < 0.001$; ^ — statistically significant difference compared to the moderate adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ^^ — $p < 0.01$; ^^ — $p < 0.001$.

Chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association between ART adherence and family status ($\chi^2 = 41.1, df = 4, p < 0.001$).

The analysis showed that in the high adherence group, the number of children from complete families was twice as high as those from incomplete families (66.7% vs. 33.3%). In contrast, no statistically significant differences were found between family types in the moderate and low adherence groups.

We also examined the relationship between different levels of ART adherence and the family's income level. Figure 2 presents the overall distribution of families by income level.

Figure 2. Distribution of Families Raising HIV-Infected Children by Income Level

The majority of families raising children included in our study had an average or below-average income level (a total of 69.1%). One in five children (20.1%) was raised in a family with a high income level. A smaller proportion (10.8%) came from low-income families.

An analysis of the distribution of children by ART adherence level across different family income groups yielded the following results (see Table 2).

Table 2. ART Adherence Levels Among HIV-Infected Children by Family Income Level

Family Income Level	Adherence Levels					
	Low		Average		High	
	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%
Low	22	20,2±3,8	18	10,3±2,3*	35	8,5±1,4**
Below average	51	46,8±4,8	87	49,7±3,8	86	20,9±2,0***^^^
Average	26	23,9±4,1	46	26,3±3,3	184	44,8±2,5***^^^
High	10	9,2±2,8	24	13,7±2,6	106	25,8±2,2***^^^

*Note:— statistically significant difference compared to the low adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ** — $p < 0.01$; *** — $p < 0.001$;*

^ — statistically significant difference compared to the moderate adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ^^ — $p < 0.01$; ^^ — $p < 0.001$.

An analysis of the association between adherence and family income revealed a moderate correlation ($r = 0.53$).

Chi-square analysis confirmed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 84.5, df = 6, p < 0.01$).

The analysis revealed that in the group of children with high adherence levels, families with high and average income predominated (a total of 70.6%). In contrast, among children with low adherence, the majority came from families with low or below-average income levels (a total of 67%).

It is worth noting that families with low income were significantly more frequent among cases with low adherence compared to those with moderate adherence ($p < 0.05$) and high adherence ($p < 0.01$). The highest proportion of high-income families was observed significantly more often in the high adherence group compared to the moderate and low adherence groups ($p < 0.001$).

A particularly important factor influencing adherence—especially in childhood—is the identity of the person responsible for ensuring the proper administration of medications. Depending on the child’s age, this role may be fulfilled by parents, close relatives, legal guardians, healthcare providers, or, as the child matures, by the child themselves. We analyzed this factor, and the results are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Persons Responsible for Ensuring ART Adherence

The diagram clearly illustrates that in the majority of cases in our sample, ART adherence was ensured by the patients themselves. This can be explained primarily by the age characteristics of the cohort. As mentioned earlier, the vast majority of HIV-positive pediatric patients in Uzbekistan today (as well as in our study sample) are adolescents aged 15–18 years, an age at which adherence can be maintained independently by the patient.

It is noteworthy that in none of the cases was adherence supported by a social worker. This highlights several organizational issues in the provision of ART services—specifically, the underdeveloped system of social and volunteer support for children and adolescents living with HIV. Most social initiatives remain focused on the adult patient population.

We then analyzed the relationship between ART adherence levels and the characteristics of the persons responsible for ensuring adherence. These results are presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Assessment of the Relationship Between ART Adherence Levels Among HIV-Infected Children and the Persons Responsible for Ensuring Adherence

Who ensures adherence	Adherence Levels					
	Low		Average		High	
	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%
The patient himself						
A parent	72	66,1±4,5	144	82,3±2,9**	371	90,3±1,5***^^
Relatives/guardians	19	17,4±3,6	24	13,7±2,6	21	5,1±1,1***^^
Healthcare workers	10	9,2±2,8	6	3,4±1,4	10	2,4±0,8*
Who ensures adherence	8	7,3±2,5	1	0,6±0,6**	9	2,2±0,7*

*Note:— statistically significant difference compared to the low adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ** — $p < 0.01$; *** — $p < 0.001$; ^ — statistically significant difference compared to the moderate adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ^^ — $p < 0.01$; ^^ — $p < 0.001$.*

Chi-square analysis revealed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 48.5$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.01$).

The data presented in the table show that in cases of high adherence, the main role in ensuring adherence was played by the patient themselves ($p < 0.001$). This reflects a high level of motivation among adolescents regarding their health, which is often lacking when medication adherence is managed by third parties—even close relatives.

This hypothesis is supported by the data from the low adherence group, where 33.9% of cases (one in three children) involved medication being administered under the supervision of relatives or other individuals, compared to only 9.7% in the high adherence group. It is also notable that in the moderate adherence group, a substantial proportion of cases (17.7%) were managed by someone other than the patient.

These findings emphasize the importance of patient education and motivation as key components in achieving satisfactory adherence. In addition to situations where caregivers may face serious social or medical challenges (e.g., substance use, poor health, low awareness), there may be seemingly harmless factors—such as forgetfulness, being overworked, or having multiple children—that can negatively impact ART effectiveness in children.

In this context, the educational background of the individuals responsible for ensuring adherence in our sample warrants special attention. Overall, among those overseeing the child's medication intake, 1% had only primary education, 60.4% had secondary/vocational education, and 38.6% held a university degree.

We further analyzed the educational level of these individuals in relation to the ART adherence levels observed in children from our study cohort. The results are presented in Table 4.

The data in Table 5 show that primary education was observed only in the group with low adherence. Compared to this group, the proportion of caregivers with higher education was significantly greater in both the moderate and high adherence groups ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, the group with low adherence was characterized by a significantly higher share of individuals with secondary vocational education (69.7%) compared to the other groups ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, analysis of certain socio-demographic characteristics of HIV-infected children receiving ART revealed several factors that may influence adherence. These include family status

(complete or incomplete), family income level, the identity of the person responsible for adherence (the patient themselves or others), and the educational status of those overseeing medication administration.

Table 4. Educational Status of Individuals Responsible for Ensuring ART Adherence in Children

Educational status of people ensuring adherence to ART	Adherence Levels					
	Low		Low		Low	
	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%	absolute figure	%
Primary						
Secondary	7	6,4±2,3	0		0	
Higher	76	69,7±4,4	98	56,0±3,8*	246	59,9±2,4*
Educational status of people ensuring adherence to ART	26	23,9±4,1	77	44,0±3,8** *	165	40,1±2,4** *

Note:— statistically significant difference compared to the low adherence group ($p < 0.05$);

*** — $p < 0.01$; *** — $p < 0.001$;*

^ — statistically significant difference compared to the moderate adherence group ($p < 0.05$); ^^ — $p < 0.01$; ^^ — $p < 0.001$.

An analysis of the association between adherence and the educational level of individuals responsible for ART adherence revealed a weak correlation ($r = 0.38$).

Chi-square analysis showed a statistically significant association ($\chi^2 = 47.5$, $df = 4$, $p < 0.001$).

CONCLUSION

This study established that adherence to antiretroviral therapy (ART) among HIV-infected children is influenced by a range of socio-demographic factors. The most significant predictors included family status (complete vs. incomplete), household income level, the child's direct involvement in therapy adherence, and the educational level of individuals responsible for administering treatment.

Our analysis showed that a high level of adherence was significantly more common among children from complete families, those with medium to high income, and in cases where the patient themselves ensured adherence. Additionally, the presence of higher education in caregivers positively correlated with adherence. In contrast, factors such as age and gender did not show statistically significant influence.

The use of statistical methods—including the chi-square (χ^2) test, Student's t-test, and Pearson correlation analysis—together with IBM SPSS Statistics software enabled the development of a predictive model identifying statistically significant relationships and facilitating the early detection of children at risk for low adherence.

The findings underscore the importance of an individualized approach in supporting HIV-infected children. Special attention should be given to educating caregivers and parents and to fostering a sense of responsibility and awareness among adolescents themselves. The predictive model developed in this study can serve as a basis for improving adherence support programs and increasing the overall effectiveness of ART in pediatric populations.

REFERENCES

1. Nachega JB, Sam-Agudu NA, Mofenson LM, et al. Adherence to antiretroviral therapy in children and adolescents in low- and middle-income countries: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet Child Adolesc Health*. 2022;6(6):408–23. doi:10.1016/S2352-4642(22)00002-1.
2. World Health Organization. HIV treatment and care [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2023 [cited 2025 May 20]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/hiv-aids>
3. Bekker LG, Hosek S. Building our youth for the future: the importance of adolescent-friendly HIV care. *J Int AIDS Soc*. 2018;21(Suppl 1):e25056. doi:10.1002/jia2.25056.
4. Cluver L, Hodes R, Toska E, et al. Child and adolescent adherence to antiretroviral therapy: a systematic review. *AIDS*. 2015;29(Suppl 3):S163–9. doi:10.1097/QAD.0000000000000695.
5. Zhukov AY, Nikitina IV, Chekalina SY. The problem of adherence to antiretroviral therapy among adolescents with HIV infection. *Infect Dis (Mosk)*. 2020;18(1):45–50. (In Russian)
6. Isakova TA, Mamedova AI, Ashurova NS. Factors influencing ART adherence in children under outpatient observation. *Curr Pediatr*. 2021;20(3):110–5. (In Russian)
7. IBM Corp. IBM SPSS Statistics. User Guide. Version 26. Moscow: IBM Corp.; 2020. 156 p. (In Russian)
8. Haberer JE, Mellins CA. Pediatric adherence to HIV antiretroviral therapy. *Curr HIV/AIDS Rep*. 2009;6(4):194–200.
9. Nabukeera-Barungi N, Kalibala S, Kekitiinwa A, et al. Adherence to antiretroviral therapy in children attending a HIV clinic in Uganda. *BMC Pediatr*. 2007;7:12.
10. Lukyanova EM, Volynets NM. HIV infection in children: modern aspects of therapy. *Pediatr Pharmacol*. 2018;15(4):270–5. (In Russian)
11. Roshchina YM, Orlova EV. Social aspects of adherence to therapy in children with chronic diseases. *Med Care*. 2022;1:20–4. (In Russian)
12. UNAIDS. Start Free, Stay Free, AIDS Free: Final Report 2022 [Internet]. Geneva: UNAIDS; 2022 [cited 2025 May 20]. Available from: <https://www.unaids.org>
13. Rudnev VA, Kolesnikova IP. Psychosocial characteristics of adolescents living with HIV. *Soc Clin Psychiatry*. 2019;29(3):69–74. (In Russian)
14. World Health Organization. Adolescent HIV testing, counselling and care: implementation guidance for health providers and planners [Internet]. Geneva: WHO; 2014 [cited 2025 May 20]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241506168>
15. Joint United Nations Programme on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS). Global AIDS Update 2023 [Internet]. Geneva: UNAIDS; 2023 [cited 2025 May 20]. Available from: <https://www.unaids.org>